

Table 1. Representative Strategies for the Synthesis of HGS.

Synthesis Method	Precursor	Template	Graphitic Quality	Structural Precision	Scalability	Application	Ref.
Hard-template	Ethanol	Al ₂ O ₃ , TiO ₂ , MgO SiO ₂	Good graphitic structure	Core-shell nanostructures with uniform graphene coating	High	Electrochemical energy storage (battery electrodes)	[35]
Hard-template	Benzene	In situ formed MgO	Few-layer graphitic graphene shells with high sp ² carbon	Uniform graphene coating around nanoparticles,	High	Li-S Battery	[36]
Hard-template	Ferrocene	SiO ₂	High-quality graphitic graphene layers	High structural control over few-layer graphene sheets	High	Sensors, nanoelectronics, energy devices	[86]
Hard-template	PAN	PMMA	mostly amorphous/partially graphitized carbon	Uniform hollow carbon nanospheres	Moderate	Catalytic supports/energy storage	[87]
Hard-template	ZIF-67 (2-methylimidazole-based MOF)	PS	Nitrogen-doped graphitic carbon framework formed after carbonization	Single-holed hollow Co-N-C nanostructure with controlled morphology	Moderate	Oxidase-mimicking nanozyme for chemiluminescent biosensing of β-galactosidase	[88]
Soft-template	Resorcinol + Formaldehyde	Pluronic surfactant micelles	Low-moderate	Highly uniform	Moderate	Li-S batteries	[64]
Soft-template	Dopamine	oil-water emulsion droplets	Low-moderate	Highly uniform	Moderate	Energy storage, catalysis, adsorption	[66]
Soft-template	Coal tar pitch	no external template	High graphitic quality	Nanoporous carbon with graphene walls but less precise morphology control	High	Energy storage (supercapacitors), adsorption	[67]
Soft-template	2,4-Dihydroxybenzoic acid	P123/SO emulsion (PEG-assisted)	Mostly amorphous	controllable shell structures	Moderate	Dye adsorption	[89]
Self-template	Phenolic resin precursors	Silica-like Stöber-derived spheres	Moderate graphitic carbon after heat treatment	Highly uniform hollow spheres	High	Adsorption, catalysis, energy storage	[49]
Self-template	ZIF-8 MOF + Mo (CO) ₆	ZIF-8 framework as sacrificial template	ZIF-8 framework as sacrificial template	Precise nanocage morphology preserved during pyrolysis	Moderate	Heterogeneous catalysis	[50]
Self-template	Metal-organic frameworks	Intrinsic MOF porous framework	Moderate graphitic ordering depending on pyrolysis temperature	Good structural retention of porous framework	Moderate	Energy storage and electrocatalysis	[71]

Self-template	Zn-Co MOF precursors	MOF-derived hollow core-shell template	Conductive N-doped carbon matrix	High control of single-hole hollow core-shell structure	Moderate	Lithium-ion battery electrode materials	[75]
Self-template	Metal-organic frameworks	MOF	Moderate-high graphitic carbon after pyrolysis	Good control of hollow architecture and mesoporous shells	Moderate	Energy storage, catalysis, adsorption	[77]